

S-SUBSTITUTED THIOUREAS AS ANALYTICAL REAGENTS. PART II. S-METHYLTHIOUREA SULPHATE AS A REAGENT FOR SILVER

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S-Methylthiourea sulphate has been successfully employed as a gravimetric reagent for silver. The method takes advantage of the formation of a highly insoluble, stable precipitate of silver methylmercaptide, AgCH_3S , which coagulates rapidly and may be filtered easily. The precipitation should be done in an ammoniacal medium. A quantitative separation of silver from zinc has also been made from a strongly ammoniacal solution containing ammonium nitrate. The precipitate of AgCH_3S is less soluble than AgCl .

Siddhanta and Kundu (this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 655) discussed the scope of using S-substituted thioureas as analytical reagents, and successfully employed S-methylthiourea sulphate as a gravimetric reagent for copper and nickel. In the present work the same reagent has been utilised in the gravimetric estimation of silver and its separation from zinc.

Klason (*Ber.*, 1887, 20 3410) described the preparation of silver methylmercaptide. The same compound has been prepared by us as a highly insoluble precipitate in a different way by adding ammonia to a mixture of S-methylthiourea sulphate and silver nitrate in an aqueous solution. The precipitation is quantitative and the precipitate is stable enough to be dried at $110-25^\circ$ to the stoichiometric composition of AgCH_3S .

A separation of silver from zinc in strong ammoniacal solution containing ammonium nitrate has also been made, as zinc is not precipitated under this condition, presumably due to the greater solubility product of $\text{Zn}(\text{CH}_3\text{S})_2$.

The estimation of silver, if present singly, is very rapid, and takes about $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours. The precipitate is highly insoluble. Moreover, the precipitate coagulates readily, permitting very easy and quick filtration. For the separation of silver from zinc, a single precipitation is sufficient.

In the estimation of silver by the usual method as silver chloride, the solubility of silver chloride in water causes a rather large error, and a correction becomes necessary. Moreover, the method is time consuming, requiring four to five hours for completion. The precipitated silver chloride is highly reactive to light; while silver methylmercaptide is not.

EXPERIMENTAL

Silver methylmercaptide (AgCH_3S) was obtained as a light yellow precipitate by mixing a solution containing an excess of S-methylthiourea sulphate (B.D.H. Lab. reagent)

to a hot ammoniacal solution of silver nitrate. (Found: Ag, 69.49. Calc. for AgCH_3S : Ag, 69.65%). Conversion factor, AgCH_3S : Ag = 0.6965.

Silver solutions were prepared by dissolving silver nitrate in which silver was estimated as silver chloride (Treadwell and Hall, "Analytical Chemistry", Vol. II, 1935, p. 297), applying corrections for the solubility of silver chloride in the wash liquid. Zinc solutions were prepared by dissolving zinc sulphate, in which zinc was estimated as pyrophosphate (*ibid.*, p. 146). All the above estimations were made in duplicate with exactly concordant results.

All measured volumes were taken from the same calibrated N.P.L. standard burette consistently using a float. All weighings were made by a "semi-micro balance" using a calibrated weight box.

Estimation of Silver

About two-fold excess of *S*-methylthiourea sulphate, dissolved in minimum quantity of water, was added to different measured volumes of silver nitrate solutions, each diluted to about 150 c.c. The mixture was heated just to boiling and made strongly ammoniacal (2 to 3 c.c. of 3*N* ammonia solution), when a yellowish white curdy precipitate of silver methylmercaptide was formed. The precipitate was kept at about 80° for nearly 15 to 30 minutes, filtered through a Gooch crucible (No. 3), washed with warm water and finally with alcohol and dried at 125° to a constant weight. Results are shown in Table I. The precipitation, however, was found to be incomplete at room temperature.

TABLE I

Ag taken.	Wt. of AgMeS.	Ag found.	Error.	Ag taken.	Wt. of AgMeS.	Ag found.	Error.
0.00603 g.	0.0088 g.	0.00613 g.	+0.10 mg.	0.1206 g.	0.2594 g.	0.1807 g.	+0.10 mg.
0.01206	0.0173	0.01204	-0.02	0.2408	0.3452	0.2404	-0.4
0.01809	0.0262	0.01824	+0.15	0.3010	0.4324	0.3011	+0.1
0.03618	0.0520	0.03624	+0.06	0.3612	0.5189	0.3613	+0.1
0.1204	0.1730	0.1204	±0.00	0.4816	0.6917	0.4817	+0.1

Effect of Drying Temperature and Time.—It has been observed that a constant weight of the precipitate is attained on drying at 110-25° for about 45 minutes to 1 hour. In sharp contrast to the cases of most other sulphur-containing organic reagents, the tendency of the precipitate to be oxidised by air is practically nil - even when it is heated for up to 12 hours or possibly longer at the above temperature.

Effect of Variation of Concentration of Ammonia and p_{H} .—It will be evident from Table II that the results are most accurate if the precipitation is made in the p_{H} range of 7.4 to 10.7. There is, however, a slight tendency of the precipitate for colloid formation at higher ammonia concentrations.

TABLE II
(Three-fold excess of the reagent was added)

0.3N-Ammonia soln. added.	pH.	Ag taken = 0.1204 g. Wt. of AgMeS.	Ag found.	Error.
0.5 c.c.	6.20	0.1126 g.	Large; ammonia added is insufficient to liberate the free base completely.	
1	7.44	0.1729	0.1204 g.	±0.00 mg.
2	8.93	0.1730	0.1204	±0.00
3	9.34	0.1728	0.1203	-0.1
4	9.56	0.1729	0.1204	±0.00
5	9.61	0.1728	0.1203	-0.1
10	10.70	0.1727	0.1202	-0.2
20	10.93	0.1726	0.1201	-0.3
25	11.01	0.1725	0.1201	-0.3

Effect of Keeping the Soln. after Precipitation for different lengths of Time.—From Table III it will be seen that variation of the intervals between the precipitation and filtration does not affect the result.

TABLE III
Ag taken = 0.1204 g.

Time interval (mins.)	...	5	15	30	1080
Wt. of Ag methylmercaptide (g.)	...	0.1732	0.1731	0.1729	0.1728
Ag found (g.)	...	0.1206	0.1205	0.1204	0.1203
Error (mg.)	...	+0.2	+0.1	±0.00	-0.1

Effect of Variation of Amount of the Reagent.—It is evident from Table IV that with the reagent not less than one and half times the amount stoichiometrically required, fairly accurate results are obtained.

TABLE IV

Ag taken = 0.1204 g. Ammonia soln. (0.3N) added = 2 c.c.

Silver : reagent (molar ratio).	Wt. of AgMeS.	Ag found.	Error.	Silver : reagent (molar ratio).	Wt. of AgMeS.	Ag. found.	Error.
1:1	0.1726 g.	0.1201 g.	-0.3 mg.	1:2	0.1729 g.	0.1204 g.	±0.00 mg.
1:1.25	0.1725	0.1201	-0.3	1:2.5	0.1730	0.1204	±0.00
1:1.5	0.1728	0.1203	-0.1	1:6	0.1729	0.1203	-0.1
1:1.75	0.1730	0.1204	±0.00				

Separation of Silver from Zinc

To a solution containing a mixture of measured volumes of silver nitrate and zinc sulphate solutions, not exceeding approximately 60 c.c. in volume, about 3 g. of ammonium nitrate and four-fold excess of the reagent were added. On diluting the solution to about 100 c.c., it was heated and approximately 10 c.c. of liquor ammonia

was added. The yellowish white precipitate of silver methylmercaptide formed was immediately filtered, washed successively with hot solutions containing 2% ammonium nitrate and 5% ammonium hydroxide, then with water, dried at 110-25° for an hour and weighed. The filtrate was immediately acidified with HCl, the volume reduced to 100 c.c. by evaporation, and zinc was estimated as zinc pyrophosphate. The results are shown in Table V.

TABLE V

Ag taken.	Zn taken.	Wt. of AgMeS	Wt. of Zn pyrophosphate.	Ag found.	Zn found.	Error (in mg.).	
						Ag.	Zn.
0.1204 g.	0.1041 g	0.1733 g.	0.2445 g.	0.1207 g.	0.1049 g.	+0.3	+0.8
"	"	0.1732	0.2448	0.1206	0.1050	+0.2	+0.9
"	"	0.1737	0.2448	0.1209	0.1050	+0.5	+0.9
"	0.0312	0.1730	0.0738	0.1204	0.0317	±0.0	+0.43
"	"	0.1732	0.0742	0.1206	0.0318	+0.2	+0.60
Nil	0.1041	...	0.2434	...	0.1044	...	+0.30

It is evident from the above table that the results of silver are accurate, but those for zinc are consistently about 1% high. If the weight of zinc pyrophosphate be arbitrarily diminished by 1% of its value, then we may expect correct results. The consistent 1% positive error in zinc may be due to the presence of silver that has escaped precipitation as mercaptide, since with increasing alkalinity (higher ammonia concentration) larger and larger negative errors have been noted in the estimation of silver (cf. Table II). The expected negative error in silver is absent, probably because of adsorption of some oxidation products of the thio-organic compounds which are possibly formed more rapidly in a high p_H medium.

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